

The Role of Recruitment and Selection Practices in Shaping Employee Organizational Commitment

Isada Mahmutović¹, Adisa Delić²

^{1,2} Department of Management, Faculty of Economics, University of Tuzla, Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

KEYWORDS: recruitment, selection, organizational commitment, affective organizational commitment, continuance organizational commitment, normative organizational commitment.

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to examine the role of recruitment and selection practices in shaping employee organizational commitment in organizations operating in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The empirical research was conducted on a sample of 128 companies from different regions of the country, and the data were collected through a survey questionnaire. The dimensional structure of the research constructs was examined using multivariate statistical procedures, after which the proposed hypotheses were tested through regression analysis. The findings indicate that recruitment and selection practices have a statistically significant and positive impact on overall organizational commitment. In addition, a significant positive relationship was identified between recruitment and selection practices and affective and normative organizational commitment, while the relationship with continuance commitment, although statistically significant, was notably weaker. These results suggest that transparent, fair, and consistently implemented recruitment and selection practices contribute more strongly to employees' emotional attachment and sense of moral obligation toward the organization than to commitment primarily driven by perceived costs of leaving. The findings are discussed in relation to existing theoretical and empirical research, emphasizing the importance of professional hiring practices for long-term employee commitment. In the specific context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, where organizations face persistent challenges related to employee retention and labor market mobility, the study emphasizes the strategic role of recruitment and selection systems as internal mechanisms for enhancing organizational commitment and fostering stable and sustainable employment relationships.

Corresponding Author:
Isada Mahmutović

Publication Date: 29 December-2025

DOI: [10.55677/GJEFR/18-2025-Vol02E12](https://doi.org/10.55677/GJEFR/18-2025-Vol02E12)

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

1. INTRODUCTION

Starting from the premise that people represent the most important resource of an organization, it logically follows that the process of recruitment and selection—if not the most important—constitutes a highly significant practice of human resource management. The recruitment process involves a systematic search for suitable candidates, from whom those who best meet job requirements are selected. In this context, it is not the quantity but rather the quality of candidates that is crucial, as only with a highly qualified workforce can an organization compete effectively in an open market. Organizations are made up of the people within them, and only through a competent and committed workforce can an organization expect success in an increasingly demanding global market (Noe et al., 2006).

Heraty and Morley (1998) point out that the long-term survival and profitability of organizations increasingly depend on the quality and contribution of their employees. According to their findings, inadequately managed recruitment and selection processes often result in additional costs and a weakened market position. Therefore, organizations seeking to enhance their competitive advantage must devote particular attention to staffing, with the aim of attracting and selecting employees whose knowledge, skills, and

professional attitudes can contribute to the achievement of organizational objectives and long-term market success (Aladwan, Bhanugopan, & D'Netto, 2015).

Although the purpose of recruitment and selection may appear straightforward, in practice, it represents a demanding and responsible process that requires considerable time, financial resources, and careful decision-making. Errors in employee selection affect not only organizational costs but may also undermine work efficiency, productivity, and the quality of interpersonal relationships within teams. Hiring unsuitable candidates can further lead to reduced employee commitment and hinder the development of teamwork. Consequently, decisions made during the recruitment and selection process are considered among the key factors of successful human resource management, given that people constitute the foundation of every organization (Tunggal, 2015).

Human resource management practices, particularly in the areas of recruitment and selection, have a significant impact on employees' ability and willingness to demonstrate creativity. A thorough exploration of the labor market and more rigorous selection procedures enable organizations to draw from a broader pool of candidates and to identify individuals with stronger creative potential, thereby ultimately raising the overall level of creativity within the organization (Jiang, Wang, & Zhao, 2012). As core human resource management functions, recruitment and selection play an important role in shaping organizational effectiveness. Well-designed recruitment and selection processes can enhance employee performance (Jiang et al., 2012) and contribute to the development of trust and commitment toward organizational goals (Jääskeläinen, Laihonon, & Lönnqvist, 2014). According to Meyer and Allen (1991), when employees perceive recruitment and selection processes as fair and transparent, they are more likely to identify with organizational goals and to develop a sense of belonging and emotional attachment to the organization. Such commitment encourages employees to perform their duties responsibly and conscientiously, which has a positive impact on individual performance and overall organizational outcomes (Newman & Sheikh, 2012). Furthermore, when human resource practices are perceived as a form of support, employees are more likely to believe that the organization cares about their well-being, motivating them to reciprocate through higher engagement and a greater willingness to invest additional effort in achieving organizational objectives (Abrokwah et al., 2018).

In light of the above, this paper seeks to examine the extent to which recruitment and selection influence employee organizational commitment in organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Bosnia and Herzegovina is a country that has been undergoing a transition process for an extended period and, despite numerous intervention measures, continues to face a shortage of qualified labor—not because qualified workers are lacking, but rather because they cannot be retained. On the contrary, Bosnia and Herzegovina is rich in high-quality human capital; however, this workforce is difficult to retain due to the opportunities offered by European and global labor markets, as well as inadequate recruitment and selection processes. In order to secure their position in the global market, organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina must devote greater attention to human resource policies, primarily by focusing on fair, ethical, and above all, transparent recruitment and selection processes that can not only attract high-quality employees but also ensure their organizational commitment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment and selection of employees represent fundamental functions within the field of human resource management and are recognized as key drivers of an organization's strategic development (Nuryani et al., 2023; Mwambela, 2024; Okolie, 2020). Improper application of these practices may lead to adverse outcomes in human resource management, including reduced employee motivation, which constitutes a significant cost for organizations. During the recruitment and selection process, human resource managers are required to carefully assess candidates' potential, ensuring that their qualifications, personal characteristics, values, and attitudes align with job requirements as well as with the organization's needs and culture. Such an approach facilitates the achievement of desired outcomes and alignment among team members, thereby fostering a harmonious work environment (Mohamed et al., 2013).

Cameron et al. (2010) emphasize that the quality of recruitment and selection strategies directly affects organizational performance outcomes. These processes form the foundation of organizational success or failure, as recruitment and selection practices must be implemented in a rigorous and professional manner, based on reliable standards. This approach enables the identification and selection of candidates who best meet organizational needs. Moreover, effective management of these processes is strongly associated with employee performance, further contributing to the achievement of organizational objectives (Dos Santos et al., 2020).

In contemporary organizations, recruitment is viewed as a process of building a pool of qualified candidates capable of meeting the requirements of vacant positions. It involves the active identification of a diverse group of potential employees possessing appropriate knowledge, skills, and developmental potential (Raghavi & Gopinathan). Although often perceived as a set of administrative activities, recruitment in conditions of intense labor market competition has a far broader strategic significance, as it represents the organization's first point of contact with prospective employees and constitutes an important component of human resource management strategy (Stoilkovska, Ilijeva, & Gjakovski, 2015). At the same time, the objective of recruitment is not to attract the largest possible number of applicants, but rather to secure an optimal number of sufficiently qualified and motivated

individuals for whom job requirements are acceptable, thereby reducing selection costs and enabling efficient staffing decisions (Noe et al., 2006).

Upon completion of the recruitment process, the organization is left with a pool of candidates who possess the knowledge and capabilities required to perform the job. Since it is generally not feasible to hire all applicants, it becomes necessary to select those who best meet job requirements. This procedure, which involves the application of various assessment methods to identify the most suitable candidates, is referred to as selection (Bahtijarević-Šiber, 1999). Selection plays a particularly important role in human resource management, as it enables alignment between employees' capabilities and organizational needs. If inappropriate candidates are selected, organizations may encounter difficulties in achieving their goals, mission, and vision (Stoilkovska, Ilieva, & Gjakovski, 2015).

Numerous studies confirm that a high-quality selection process can produce broader organizational effects. Specifically, extensive candidate searches and more rigorous selection procedures are associated with higher levels of employee creativity, which in turn are linked to both administrative and technological innovations (De Winne & Sels, 2010; Jiang, Wang, & Zhao, 2012; Chowhan, 2016). Consequently, organizations increasingly expand their search for high-quality talent beyond unemployed individuals to include currently employed professionals who, although not actively seeking new positions, possess the knowledge and competencies required to fill specific roles (Kastratović, 2020).

Organizational Commitment

In the literature, organizational commitment is described in various ways; however, most authors agree that it is reflected in a strong connection between employees and the organization, its goals, and its values. Employees who feel committed to their organization tend to demonstrate higher levels of engagement, greater work efficiency, and a stronger willingness to contribute to the achievement of shared objectives. Meyer and Allen (1991) define commitment as a psychological bond that links an individual to the organization, while Steers and Lee (1982) emphasize employees' emotional attachment and their active involvement in achieving organizational goals. Similarly, Doan et al. (2020) conceptualize commitment through the degree of an individual's identification with the organization, and Neining et al. (2010) highlight that fostering such a bond represents one of the most important tasks of contemporary organizations.

In the modern business environment, characterized by rapid technological change and increasing workforce diversity, building and maintaining employee commitment has become an increasingly demanding process. Organizations today face the challenge not only of attracting highly qualified and skilled individuals, but also of retaining them and motivating long-term engagement. Given that people represent a key resource in conditions of advanced technological development, growing attention is being devoted to the ways in which a sense of belonging and commitment to the organization can be fostered. In this context, the findings of Hussain, Channa, and Bhutto (2022) indicate that the way an organization presents itself to candidates, as well as recruiters' behavior during the hiring process, can play a significant role in the development of organizational commitment, with employer image further strengthening this relationship.

Meyer and Allen (1991) distinguish three forms of commitment: affective, normative, and continuance. Affective commitment refers to emotional attachment to the organization; normative commitment is based on a sense of moral obligation; and continuance commitment arises from the perception of high costs associated with leaving the organization. These components are not mutually exclusive, as individuals may develop one form of commitment or a combination of multiple components. The three types of commitment differ in terms of their underlying motives and outcomes, with each playing a crucial role in shaping organizational performance and maintaining workforce stability (Alansaari et al., 2018).

Affective commitment may be defined as the desire to belong to an organization. It refers to a positive emotional bond between the employee and the organization. In other words, affective commitment indicates that an individual remains with the organization because they feel like a part of it. From an organizational perspective, this is the preferred type of employee–organization relationship, as committed employees wish to remain members of the organization and adopt organizational goals as their own (Ertemsir, Bal, & Bozkurt, 2017).

Continuance commitment refers to commitment based on the costs that employees associate with leaving the organization. In this form of commitment, the fewer viable alternatives employees perceive, the stronger their continuance commitment to their current employer will be (Abdul Rashid, Sambasivan, & Johari, 2003). When considering leaving the organization, employees take into account their prior personal investments and evaluate the costs and benefits of staying versus leaving, particularly when alternative employment opportunities arise. Continuance organizational commitment is more pronounced when perceived personal interests and benefits associated with the current position outweigh the expected advantages offered by a new job opportunity (Lambert et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2010).

According to Allen and Meyer (1990), normative commitment represents a "belief in one's responsibility toward the organization," that is, an employee's conviction that they have a duty or obligation to remain loyal to the organization. In this sense, the employee perceives a moral obligation to continue working for the current organization, regardless of the possibility that another organization might offer more favorable conditions, such as higher pay, better benefits, improved working hours, opportunities for advancement, or additional education.

Recruitment, Selection, and Organizational Commitment

Armstrong and Shimizu (2007) emphasize that recruitment strategy has a direct impact on the level of employee commitment within an organization, noting that the potential for long-term engagement can already be identified in the early stages of recruitment. Brown et al. (2011) highlight that a well-structured recruitment process significantly contributes to organizational success, as it influences employees' degree of identification with the organization and its overall effectiveness. The recruitment process enables the assessment not only of candidates' professional competencies but also of their alignment with organizational culture, while simultaneously providing candidates with the opportunity to evaluate the suitability of the work environment. This two-way process strengthens mutual trust and forms the foundation for long-term commitment and sustainable organizational success (Alansaari et al., 2018).

When an organization adopts a strategic approach to recruitment and selection practices, it does not reduce employment to a mere administrative procedure; rather, it shapes a work environment in which employees feel recognized and encouraged to contribute to their full potential. Such an approach facilitates the achievement of organizational goals while simultaneously strengthening long-term relationships based on mutual trust. As a result, employees develop a stronger sense of belonging and higher levels of organizational commitment (Stewart & Brown, 2011). Given the high costs associated with recruitment and selection processes, fostering employee commitment plays a particularly important role, as it directly contributes to building a stable and efficient organization (Shahnawaz & Juyal, 2006).

Empirical studies indicate the significant role of recruitment and selection systems in achieving organizational outcomes. Based on an analysis of a large sample of hotels, Chand and Katou (2007) found that recruitment and selection practices have a strong positive relationship with organizational performance, with their impact being most evident in profitability. Although selective hiring may contribute to improved organizational outcomes, the findings of Si and Li (2012) suggest that it does not necessarily have a direct effect on employee behavior. Accordingly, Armstrong and Taylor (2014) emphasize that human resource management policies and practices should be grounded in a deeper understanding of the factors shaping employee behavior within organizations. In this context, Agarwala (2003) points out that recruitment practices contribute to strengthening the psychological contract between employees and employers, while numerous studies confirm that well-designed recruitment and selection processes have a positive and statistically significant impact on employees' organizational commitment (Chew, Girardi, & Entekin, 2005; Paul & Anantharaman, 2004; Uraon, 2018).

Organizational innovativeness and long-term employee commitment largely depend on the quality of recruitment and selection practices. An organization's knowledge base, which forms the foundation of innovation, begins to develop through the careful attraction and selection of talented individuals, thereby creating conditions conducive to creativity and innovative behavior (Subramaniam & Youndt, 2005). Successful organizations, therefore, establish systematic recruitment networks to ensure a continuous inflow of qualified and creative talent (Jiang, Wang, & Zhao, 2012). At the same time, consistent, fair, and transparent recruitment and selection practices strengthen employee commitment and their willingness to remain with the organization over the long term, thereby enhancing organizational flexibility and sustainability (Janjua & Gulzar, 2014).

Organizational success largely depends on how effectively organizations attract, develop, and retain their employees. Research shows that carefully planned recruitment and selection processes contribute to higher workforce productivity and efficiency (Koch & McGrath, 1996). Pfeffer (1998) also argues that selective hiring enables organizations to better align their needs with employees' skills and abilities, which positively affects work quality. Conversely, improper or irresponsible implementation of recruitment practices can lead to negative consequences, such as reduced employee motivation and engagement, which in the long run represent an additional organizational cost (Mohamed et al., 2013). Therefore, in the final stages of selection, it is essential to assess not only candidates' formal qualifications but also the extent to which their values, attitudes, and working styles align with organizational culture and job requirements, thereby facilitating effective task performance and high-quality teamwork (Mohamed, Singh, Irani, & Darwish, 2013).

In addition to hiring suitable personnel, organizational success also depends on the ability to retain employees who contribute meaningfully to organizational objectives. Effective retention policies strengthen employees' sense of belonging and commitment and contribute to improved organizational performance. In contrast, retaining employees who are unmotivated, who do not contribute to organizational goals, or who damage organizational reputation may increase turnover and generate additional costs associated with repeated recruitment and selection processes (Sumarni, 2011).

Adequate professional qualification of employees represents a key prerequisite for professional competence and high job performance, as a qualified workforce directly influences the efficiency and stability of organizational functioning (Anyango et al., 2018). In this regard, recruitment and selection play a strategic role in ensuring organizational sustainability, as they enable alignment between job requirements and candidate competencies. Empirical evidence confirms that well-structured and consistently implemented recruitment processes positively affect organizational performance, whereas inadequate selection practices lead to reduced operational efficiency and overall business results (Anyango et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2012).

In their empirical study, Paul and Anantharaman (2004) found that recruitment and selection positively influence affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Uraon (2018) further confirms that this effect is most pronounced for affective

organizational commitment, while continuance commitment arises from employees' evaluation of available employment alternatives and perceived costs of leaving the organization. Such a pattern of commitment increases the likelihood of employee retention, although it does not necessarily imply a strong emotional attachment (Uraon, 2018).

Recruitment and selection thus represent key mechanisms through which organizations shape long-term employee commitment. Fair and transparent recruitment practices positively influence employees' decisions to remain with the organization and strengthen their overall level of organizational commitment (Janjua & Gulzar, 2014; Sutanto & Kurniawan, 2016). Although some studies do not find a statistically significant relationship between recruitment and selection practices and affective commitment, significant associations have been identified with continuance and normative commitment, particularly through opportunities for training and professional development (Bisharat et al., 2017; Miao et al., 2013). Furthermore, empirical findings suggest that affective organizational commitment has the most positive implications for organizational performance, whereas continuance commitment may produce limited or ambivalent effects (Meyer & Allen, 1991, 1997; Genevičiūtė-Janonienė & Endriulaitienė, 2014; Abrokwah et al., 2018).

Based on the findings of previous research, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: The implementation of an appropriate recruitment and selection system has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment.

H2: The implementation of an appropriate recruitment and selection system has a significant effect on employee affective commitment.

H3: The implementation of an appropriate recruitment and selection system has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment.

H4: The implementation of an appropriate recruitment and selection system has a significant effect on employee normative commitment.

3. METHODOLOGY

The empirical study was conducted on a sample of 128 companies from different regions of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed through the application of descriptive and inferential statistical methods. To test the research hypotheses, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed, along with the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity, as well as regression analysis. Statistical data processing was carried out using SPSS software, version 21.

The questionnaire was divided into two sections: the first section focused on recruitment and selection practices, while the second section measured organizational commitment, including its three components— affective, normative, and continuance commitment. All variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale. The study was conducted within the industrial sector, encompassing medium-sized and large organizations, to examine the relationship between recruitment and selection practices and the level of employees' organizational commitment. The reliability of the measurement instruments was assessed by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficients, and the response rate was 91.43%.

4. RESULTS

For the purposes of analyzing the initial set of items, the reliability of the measurement scales used in the study was first assessed. The reliability of the questionnaire scales was tested by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which represents a measure of internal consistency of a set of items and can take values between 0 and 1. Values closer to 1 indicate a higher level of scale reliability. As shown in Table 1, all reliability coefficients exceed 0.8, indicating that each of the scales used in the questionnaire demonstrates more than satisfactory reliability.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of questionnaire reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Recruitment and selection of employees	.907
Organizational commitment	.948
Affective commitment	.909
Continuance commitment	.879
Normative commitment	.838

Source: Authors' research

In order to reduce the initial set of variables and transform them into a smaller number of representative factors, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied. From the sets of items measuring the same constructs, dominant components explaining the largest proportion of variance were extracted, and these reduced variables were subsequently used in further statistical analyses to test the

research hypotheses. Kaiser’s criterion (eigenvalue > 1) was applied as the extraction criterion. The suitability of the data for factor analysis was confirmed by Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) values above 0.6 and statistically significant results of Bartlett’s test of sphericity ($p < 0.001$). The proportion of explained variance across components ranged from 43.45% to 62.16%. Given the limited contribution of additional components and the increased difficulty of result interpretation, only the extracted principal components presented in Table 2 were retained for further analysis.

Table 2. Extraction of the total variance of dependent and independent variables (statements) through the Principal Components Analysis

Komponente (faktori)	Initial Eigenvalues		Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
	I.E. Total	% Variance		Approx. Chi-Square	df	p
Recruitment and selection (14 items)	6,598	47,13	0,880	1102,97	91	0,000
Organizational commitment (15 items)	6,52	43,45	0,869	1010,56	105	0,000
Affective organizational commitment (8 items)	4,97	62,16	0,876	651,85	28	0,000
Continuance organizational commitment (8 items)	4,37	54,66	0,835	601,14	28	0,000
Normative organizational commitment(8 items)	3,80	47,46	0,859	328,94	28	0,000

Source: Authors’ research

Analysis of the effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee organizational commitment

Table 3 presents the results of simple linear regression analyses conducted to test the first hypothesis, which stated: “The implementation of an appropriate recruitment and selection system has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment.” In the specified hypothesis, recruitment and selection represent the independent variable, while organizational commitment represents the dependent variable.

Table 3. Effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee organizational commitment

Component (factor)	Representativeness of the regression model				Parameters of the linear regression equation		
	r	r ²	F	p	a	b	Beta
Recruitment and selection	0,644	0,415	89,3	0,000	0,0	0,644	0,644

Source: Authors’ research

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that recruitment and selection have a statistically significant impact on employee organizational commitment ($p < 0.001$). These findings support the acceptance of the first hypothesis.

Analysis of the effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee affective organizational commitment

The results of the analysis examining the impact of the recruitment and selection system on employee affective organizational commitment are presented in Table 4. As the results indicate, recruitment and selection practices have a statistically significant effect on employee affective organizational commitment ($p < 0.001$). Accordingly, the research hypothesis stating that the recruitment and selection system significantly influences employees’ affective organizational commitment is accepted.

Table 4. Effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee affective organizational commitment

Component (factor)	Representativeness of the regression model				Parameters of the linear regression equation		
	r	r ²	F	p	a	b	Beta
Recruitment and selection	0,541	0,292	52,055	0,000	0,0	0,541	0,541

Source: Authors’ research

The results of the linear regression analysis show that recruitment and selection practices have a statistically significant and positive effect on employee affective organizational commitment ($r = 0.541$; $r^2 = 0.292$; $F = 52.055$; $p < 0.05$). The coefficient of determination indicates that approximately 29.2% of the variance in affective organizational commitment can be explained by variability in recruitment and selection practices. The value of the standardized regression coefficient ($\beta = 0.541$) suggests a moderately strong positive effect of the independent variable on employee affective organizational commitment.

Analysis of the effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee continuance organizational commitment

The results of the analysis examining the impact of the recruitment and selection system on employee continuance organizational commitment are presented in Table 5. The findings indicate that recruitment and selection practices have a statistically significant positive effect on continuance organizational commitment ($p < 0.001$).

Table 5. Effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee continuance organizational commitment

Component (factor)	Representativeness of the regression model				Parameters of the linear regression equation		
	r	r ²	F	p	a	b	Beta
Recruitment and selection	0,268	0,072	9,7	0,002	0,0	0,268	0,268

Source: Authors' research

The results of the linear regression analysis are statistically significant, indicating that the recruitment and selection system is a significant predictor of employee continuance organizational commitment. The regression coefficient is 0.268, while the coefficient of determination is 0.072 and statistically significant, meaning that 7.2% of the variance in continuance organizational commitment is explained by the recruitment and selection system.

Analysis of the effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee normative organizational commitment

The results of the simple linear regression analysis presented in Table 6 indicate that the recruitment and selection system has a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and positive effect on employee normative organizational commitment, with an effect size of $b = 0.544$. Accordingly, the research hypothesis is accepted.

Table 6. Effect of the recruitment and selection system on employee normative organizational commitment

Component (factor)	Representativeness of the regression model				Parameters of the linear regression equation		
	r	r ²	F	p	a	b	Beta
Recruitment and selection	0,544	0,296	52,9	0,000	0,0	0,544	0,544

Source: Authors' research

The results of the linear regression analysis are statistically significant, indicating that the recruitment and selection system is a significant predictor of normative organizational commitment. The regression coefficient amounts to 0.544, while the coefficient of determination is 0.296 and statistically significant, meaning that 29.6% of the variance in normative organizational commitment is explained by the recruitment and selection system.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the empirical study clearly confirm the significant role of the recruitment and selection system in shaping employee organizational commitment in Bosnian and Herzegovinian organizations. The findings indicate that well-designed and consistently implemented recruitment and selection practices have a statistically significant and positive effect on overall organizational commitment ($r = 0.644$; $r^2 = 0.415$; $p < 0.001$), thereby confirming the first hypothesis. These results are consistent with previous studies emphasizing that carefully designed recruitment and selection processes have a positive and statistically significant impact on employee commitment (Chew, Girardi, & Entekin, 2005; Paul & Anantharaman, 2004; Uraon, 2018), and that fair and transparent hiring practices strengthen employee decisions to remain with the organization and increase their level of commitment (Janjua & Gulzar, 2014; Sutanto & Kurniawan, 2016). In the context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, where retaining qualified employees is particularly challenging due to the attractiveness of external labor markets, the relatively high proportion of explained variance (41.5%) suggests that "internal" management processes nevertheless have a measurable potential to shape employee relationships with their organizations.

The impact of recruitment and selection on affective commitment is statistically significant and moderately strong ($r = 0.541$; $r^2 = 0.292$; $p < 0.001$), thus confirming the second hypothesis. This finding is consistent with studies highlighting that recruitment practices influence employee identification with the organization and strengthen emotional attachment, particularly when the selection process is professional and when there is a good fit between candidates and organizational culture (Alansaari et al., 2018; Stewart & Brown, 2011). Moreover, the results align with the argument that transparent and fair recruitment and selection processes increase the likelihood of identification with organizational goals and the development of a sense of belonging (Meyer & Allen, 1991), which in turn may lead to more responsible behavior and improved performance (Newman & Sheikh, 2012). However, the findings of this study are not consistent with the conclusions of Bisharat et al. (2017) and Miao et al. (2013), who reported no significant relationship between recruitment and selection practices and affective commitment.

Continuance organizational commitment shows a statistically significant but weaker positive effect of recruitment and selection practices ($r = 0.268$; $r^2 = 0.072$; $p = 0.002$), thereby confirming the third hypothesis. This finding is consistent with the theoretical understanding of continuance commitment as a component primarily based on the assessment of the costs of leaving the organization and the availability of alternatives (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Abdul Rashid, Sambasivan, & Johari, 2003). It is also in line with evidence suggesting that continuance commitment arises from a “cost–benefit” evaluation of staying and may be less strongly associated with the quality of human resource management practices compared to affective and normative commitment (Uraon, 2018). The results are compatible with studies confirming that recruitment and selection may be significantly related to continuance commitment (Paul & Anantharaman, 2004), while simultaneously supporting the notion that continuance commitment has more ambivalent implications and relies less on relational and emotional factors (Genevičiūtė-Janonienė & Endriulaitienė, 2014; Meyer & Allen, 1997). In the Bosnian and Herzegovinian context, the relatively low proportion of explained variance (7.2%) can be further understood through the strong influence of external factors, particularly the availability of alternative employment opportunities in the European Union labor market.

Normative organizational commitment demonstrates a statistically significant and moderately strong positive relationship with recruitment and selection practices ($r = 0.544$; $r^2 = 0.296$; $p < 0.001$), thus confirming the fourth hypothesis. This finding suggests that fair, transparent, and professionally managed recruitment processes can foster the development of loyalty, responsibility, and a sense of moral obligation among employees toward the organization, which is consistent with previous research (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Janjua & Gulzar, 2014; Sutanto & Kurniawan, 2016). Furthermore, high-quality recruitment systems contribute to strengthening the psychological contract between employees and the organization (Agarwala, 2003), which is particularly relevant for normative commitment, as it is shaped through the internalization of organizational values and perceptions of fair treatment. The stronger impact of recruitment and selection on normative compared to continuance commitment may be partly explained by the specific socio-cultural context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, where employees—particularly older generations—often exhibit a strong sense of moral obligation toward organizations that have shown trust in them.

Overall, the synthesis of results indicates that recruitment and selection contribute most strongly to overall organizational commitment, with the most pronounced effects observed for normative and affective commitment (approximately 29%), while continuance commitment is substantially less explained by the recruitment and selection system (approximately 7%). This pattern is consistent with arguments suggesting that affective commitment generates the most positive implications for organizational performance, whereas continuance commitment may have more limited effects (Meyer & Allen, 1991, 1997; Abrokwhah et al., 2018). Consequently, greater transparency in recruitment and selection processes leads to stronger employee attachment to the organization, thereby creating a foundation for stable and long-term relationships between employees and organizations.

6. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that recruitment and selection have a positive impact on employee organizational commitment in Bosnian and Herzegovinian organizations, thereby confirming the fundamental assumption regarding their strategic importance. The most pronounced effects were identified for affective and normative commitment, while the impact on continuance commitment was of a weaker intensity. This pattern suggests that the quality of hiring practices contributes more strongly to the development of employees’ emotional attachment and sense of loyalty than to their decision to remain in the organization solely due to perceived costs of leaving.

Based on the results, it is recommended that organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina devote particular attention to the professionalization and transparency of recruitment and selection processes. Clearly defined hiring criteria, consistent application of procedures, and open communication with candidates can contribute to better alignment between employee values and organizational culture, thereby strengthening affective and normative commitment in the long term. The findings suggest that it is more effective to invest in practices that foster a sense of belonging, trust, and reciprocity.

The conducted research included medium-sized and large organizations from the industrial sector, and therefore, the obtained results cannot be fully generalized to other sectors or to small organizations. For this reason, future research could extend the sample to include organizations from different sectors and industries and adopt a longitudinal research design to examine the long-term effects of recruitment and selection systems on various dimensions of organizational commitment.

The theoretical contribution of this study lies in confirming the differentiated impact of recruitment and selection systems on individual dimensions of organizational commitment within a transitional context. The practical implications indicate that organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina should place particular emphasis on the development of ethical, consistent, and transparent selection procedures, not only to attract high-quality employee but also to ensure their long-term organizational commitment.

REFERENCES

1. Abrokwhah, E., Yuhui, G., Agyare, R., & Asamany, A. (2018). Recruitment and selection practices among non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Ghana. *Labor History*, 59(2), 185-201.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0023656X.2018.1422417>

2. Abdul Rashid, Z., Sambasivan, M., & Johari, J. (2003). The influence of corporate culture and organisational commitment on performance. *Journal of management development*, 22(8), 708-728.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710310487873>
3. Abrokwah, E., Yuhui, G., Agyare, R., & Asamany, A. (2018). Recruitment and selection practices among non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Ghana. *Labor History*, 59(2), 185-201.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0023656X.2018.1422417>
4. Agarwala, T. (2003). Innovative human resource practices and organizational commitment: An empirical investigation. *International journal of human resource management*, 14(2), 175-197. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0958519021000029072>
5. Aladwan, K., Bhanugopan, R., & D'Netto, B. (2015). The effects of human resource management practices on employees' organisational commitment. *International journal of organizational Analysis*, 23(3), 472-492.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-11-2014-0822>
6. Alansaari, O., Yusoff, R. B. M. D., & Ismail, F. (2019). The mediating effect of employee commitment on recruitment process towards organizational performance in UAE organizations. *Management Science Letters*, 9(1), 169-182. doi: 10.5267/j.msl.2018.10.007
7. Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of occupational psychology*, 63(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>
8. Anyango, E., Walter, O. B., & Muya, J. (2018). Effects of recruitment and selection criteria on organizational performance at Kisii University, Kenya. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, 4(10), 271-282.
9. Armstrong, C. E., & Shimizu, K. (2007). A review of approaches to empirical research on the resource-based view of the firm. *Journal of management*, 33(6), 959-986. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206307307645>
10. Armstrong M., Taylor S. (2014). *Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, 13th Edition. Kogan Page. London.
11. Bahtijarević - Šiber, F. (1999). *Management ljudskih potencijala*. Golden marketing. Zagreb.
12. Bisharat, H., Obeidat, B., Alrowwad, A. A., Tarhini, A., & Mukattash, I. (2016). The effect of human resource management practices on organizational commitment in chain pharmacies in Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12(1), 1-50.
13. Brown, N. J., Newell, C. A., Stanley, S., Chen, J. E., Perrin, A. J., Kajala, K., & Hibberd, J. M. (2011). Independent and parallel recruitment of preexisting mechanisms underlying C4 photosynthesis. *Science*, 331(6023), 1436-1439.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1201248>
14. Cameron, L., Miller, P., & Frew, E. (2009). Relationship marketing in the recruitment and retention of service industry staff in family-owned businesses. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 9(1), 71-91.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15332840902942735>
15. Chand, M., & Katou, A. A. (2007). The impact of HRM practices on organisational performance in the Indian hotel industry. *Employee relations*, 29(6), 576-594. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01425450710826096>
16. Chew, J., Girardi, A., & Entekin, L. (2005). Retaining Core Staff: The impact of human resource practices on organisational commitment. *Journal of Comparative International Management*, 8(2), 23-42.
17. Chowhan, J. (2016). Unpacking the black box: understanding the relationship between strategy, HRM practices, innovation and organizational performance. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 26(2), 112-133. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12097>
18. De Winne, S., & Sels, L. (2010). Interrelationships between human capital, HRM and innovation in Belgian start-ups aiming at an innovation strategy. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(11), 1863-1883.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2010.505088>
19. Doan, T. T. T., Nguyen, L. C. T., & Nguyen, T. D. N. (2020). Emotional intelligence and project success: The roles of transformational leadership and organizational commitment. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(3), 223-233. doi:10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no3.223
20. Dos Santos, A., Armanu, A., Setiawan, M., & Rofiq, A. (2020). Effect of recruitment, selection and culture of organizations on state personnel performance. *Management science letters*, 10(6), 1179-1186. doi: 10.5267/j.msl.2019.11.042
21. Ertemsir, E., Bal, Y., Bozkurt, S. (2017). A Research on Determining the Influence of HRM Practices on Increasing Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Euro-Mediterranean Studies*. 10(2), pp. 3-28.
22. Genevičiūtė-Janonienė, G., & Endriulaitienė, A. (2014). Employees' organizational commitment: Its negative aspects for organizations. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 140, 558-564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.470>
23. Heraty, N., & Morley, M. (1998). In search of good fit: policy and practice in recruitment and selection in Ireland. *Journal of management development*, 17(9), 662-685. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621719810244490>
24. Hussain, T., Channa, K. A., & Bhutto, M. H. (2024). Impact of recruitment practices on organizational commitment: mediating role of employer image. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 40(3), 605-621.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-10-2020-0176>

25. Jääskeläinen, A., Laihonen, H., & Lönnqvist, A. (2014). Distinctive features of service performance measurement. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 34(12), 1466-1486. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-02-2013-0067>
26. Janjua, B. H., & Gulzar, A. (2014). The impact of human resource practices on employee commitment and employee retention in telecom sector of Pakistan: Exploring the mediating role of employee loyalty. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 16(1), 76-81.
27. Jiang, J., Wang, S., & Zhao, S. (2012). Does HRM facilitate employee creativity and organizational innovation? A study of Chinese firms. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(19), 4025-4047. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1080/09585192.2012.690567>
28. Jiang, K., Lepak, D. P., Han, K., Hong, Y., Kim, A., & Winkler, A. L. (2012). Clarifying the construct of human resource systems: Relating human resource management to employee performance. *Human resource management review*, 22(2), 73-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2011.11.005>
29. Kastratović, N. (2020). Unapređenje procesa selekcije u organizaciji. *Zbornik radova Fakulteta tehničkih nauka u Novom Sadu*, 35(05), 849-852. <https://doi.org/10.24867/07GI10Kastratovic>
30. Koch, M. J., & McGrath, R. G. (1996). Improving labor productivity: Human resource management policies do matter. *Strategic management journal*, 17(5), 335-354. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199605\)17:5%3C335::AID-SMJ814%3E3.0.CO;2-R](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199605)17:5%3C335::AID-SMJ814%3E3.0.CO;2-R)
31. Lambert, E. G., Hogan, N. L., & Keena, L. D. (2015). The impact of job attitudes on private correctional staff's continuance and affective organizational commitment. *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 10(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361610.2015.972260>
32. Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1(1), 61-89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
33. Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research, and application*. Thousand Oaks. Sage Publications. CA.
34. Miao, Q., Newman, A., Sun, Y., & Xu, L. (2013). What factors influence the organizational commitment of public sector employees in China? The role of extrinsic, intrinsic and social rewards. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(17), 3262-3280. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.770783>
35. Mohamed, A. F., Singh, S., Irani, Z., & Darwish, T. K. (2013). An analysis of recruitment, training and retention practices in domestic and multinational enterprises in the country of Brunei Darussalam. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(10), 2054-2081. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2012.723021>
36. Morrow, P. C., & McElroy, J. C. (2001). Work commitment: conceptual and methodological developments for the management of human resources. *Human resource management review*, 11(3), 177-180.
37. Mwambela, A. (2024). Analysis of the Impact of Recruitment and Selection as a Strategic Human Resource Management Tool on Organisational Performance in Zambia. *Journal of Management Studies and Development*, 3(03), 193-210. <https://doi.org/10.56741/jmsd.v3i03.620>
38. Newman, A., & Sheikh, A. Z. (2012). Organizational rewards and employee commitment: a Chinese study. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 27(1), 71-89. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683941211193866>
39. Noe, R. A., Hollenback, J. R., Gerhart, B., Wright, P. M. (2006). *Manadžment ljudskih potencijala*. Mate. Zagreb.
40. Nuryani, Y., Zayroni, A., Santoso, A., & Anshori, M. (2023). The role of human resource management in implementing a recruitment and selection system for competitive advantage. *Economic and Business Horizon*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.54518/ebh.2.3.2023.190>
41. Okolie, U. C. (2020). Effect of diversity management on human resource management: Recruitment and selection in focus. *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*, 20(2), 63-86.
42. Paul, A. K., & Anantharaman, R. N. (2004). Influence of HRM practices on organizational commitment: A study among software professionals in India. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 15(1), 77-88. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.1088>
43. Pfeffer, J. (1998). Seven practices of successful organizations. *California management review*, 40(2), 96-124. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125619884002001>
44. Raghavi, K., & Gopinathan, N. (2013). Role of human resources as change agent in enabling equal opportunity practices. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 1(3), 300-303. DOI: 10.7763/JOEBM.2013.V1.65
45. Shahnawaz, M. G., & Juyal, R. C. (2006). Human resource management practices and organizational commitment in different organizations. *Journal of the Indian academy of applied psychology*, 32(3), 171-178.
46. Si, S., & Li, Y. (2012). Human resource management practices on exit, voice, loyalty, and neglect: Organizational commitment as a mediator. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(8), 1705-1716. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.580099>

47. Steers, R. M., & Lee, T. W. (1982). Facilitating effective performance appraisals: The role of employee commitment and organizational climate. Eugene, OR: Oregon University Graduate School of Management. Retrieved from: www.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a119413.pdf
48. Stewart, G. L., & Brown, K. G. (2019). *Human resource management*. John Wiley & Sons.
49. Stoilkovska, A., Ilieva, J., & Gjakovski, S. (2015). Equal employment opportunities in the recruitment and selection process of human resources. *UTMS Journal of Economics*, 6(2), 281-292. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/146370>
50. Subramaniam, M., & Youndt, M. A. (2005). The influence of intellectual capital on the types of innovative capabilities. *Academy of Management journal*, 48(3), 450-463. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2005.17407911>
51. Sumarni, M. (2011). Pengaruh employee retention terhadap turnover intention dan kinerja karyawan. *Akmenika Upy*, 8, 20-47.
52. Sutanto, E. M., & Kurniawan, M. (2016). The impact of recruitment, employee retention and labor relations to employee performance on batik industry in Solo City, Indonesia. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 17(2), 375-390.
53. Tunggal, A. C., & Setiawan, R. (2015). Studi Deskriptif Rekrutmen dan Seleksi pada PT. Multi Artistikacithra. *Agora*, 3(1), 647-650.
54. Uraon, R. S. (2018). Examining the impact of HRD practices on organizational commitment and intention to stay within selected software companies in India. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 20(1), 11-43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1523422317741691>
55. Wang, C. L., Indridason, T., & Saunders, M. N. (2010). Affective and continuance commitment in public private partnership. *Employee Relations*, 32(4), 396-417. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01425451011051613>